

Aggregation-Tier Designation, OT Self-Tailoring, and Velocity-Based Assurance: A Regulatory Architecture for Distributed Energy Cyber Resilience

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ABSTRACT

The DESNZ/Ofgem consultation *Reshaping Cyber Regulation in Downstream Gas and Electricity* proposes two structural reforms — a review of NIS Regulations applicability and the introduction of baseline cyber resilience requirements for over 1,400 licensed operators across the different licensed areas via the Cyber Essentials scheme. Both reforms address real and documented gaps. Their construction, however, retains the regulatory primitives calibrated in 2018 — the individual operator as the unit of analysis and static positional certification as the assurance instrument — while introducing, as the new universal baseline, an IT-focused control set misaligned with the OT-heavy system being built. These primitives were appropriate for a concentrated energy system. They are not appropriate for the distributed, OT-heavy system the UK is now building under the Clean Power 2030 ambition.

This paper sets out a three-component regulatory architecture that replaces all three primitives simultaneously: aggregation-tier designation targeting correlated risk across operators rather than individual operator size; OT self-tailoring against a recognised reference replacing uniform mandatory control lists; and velocity-based assurance anchored to a sectoral threat-intelligence function. The three components are not separable. The argument draws on the December 2025 Polish energy-sector incident, NIST SP 800-82r3, and the author's prior responsibility for OT cyber security capability at Eurasian Resources Group in Kazakhstan, whose thermal generation assets supplied approximately 17 per cent of national electricity and whose OT estates within the same holding also spanned mining and primary processing.

1 INTRODUCTION

On 27 March 2026, the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ) and the Office of Gas and Electricity Markets (Ofgem) opened a consultation, *Reshaping Cyber Regulation in Downstream Gas and Electricity*, proposing two structural reforms to cyber resilience in the Downstream Gas and Electricity (DGE) sector. The first is a review of the applicability of the Network and Information Systems (NIS) Regulations 2018 — specifically, whether the operator-size thresholds set in 2018 still capture the operators that materially affect system stability under the Clean Power 2030 ambition. The second is the introduction of baseline cyber resilience requirements for over 1,400 licensed operators across the different licensed areas (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero and Ofgem, 2026, p. 18), with Cyber Essentials (CE) and Cyber Essentials Plus (CE+) proposed as the starting reference scheme.

Both reforms address genuine gaps and respond to documented changes in the threat landscape and system composition. The argument advanced here is that their construction inherits two primitives from the 2018 regime — individual operator as unit of analysis, static positional checklist as assurance — while introducing, as the new universal baseline, an IT-focused control set: a combination calibrated for a concentrated energy system that no longer exists and is not the system being built. A reform that retains all three primitives uniformly extends a model that the same consultation document elsewhere acknowledges is no longer fit. The sections that follow set out an alternative architecture in three components, each of which is necessary and none of which is sufficient alone.

The architecture set out here is a general mechanism for any regulated critical-infrastructure sector with heterogeneous operational-technology estates, distributed operator populations, and active threat development. The present consultation is the application context — and the fit is direct.

2 THE 2018 UNIT OF ANALYSIS NO LONGER FITS

The consultation is candid about the change in system composition. Battery storage capacity is projected to increase sixfold; wind and solar capacity to nearly triple by 2030 (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero and Ofgem, 2026, p. 9). The document states explicitly: "what we view as critical has changed, as the system becomes less concentrated" (p. 9). It then offers the December 2025 CERT Polska incident as the principal contemporary evidence (foreword and pp. 9–10), in a compressed summary at p. 10: "around 30 distributed renewables assets, including wind and solar farms, a combined heat and power plant, and a company in the manufacturing sector... could have impacted over 500,000 customers."

Reading the CERT Polska report directly (CERT.PL and Ministry of Digital Affairs, 2026) decomposes this into a coordinated three-pronged campaign by a single threat actor on 29 December 2025, with materially different impact characteristics for each prong:

- **Approximately 30 wind and solar farms.** Destructive activity against substation equipment (RTUs, HMIs, protection relays) caused loss of communication with distribution system operators but did not affect ongoing electricity generation. CERT Polska states explicitly that the combined loss of capacity across all 30 facilities would not have destabilised the Polish power system even had generation been disrupted.
- **A large combined heat and power plant.** A separate attack on a single CHP facility supplying heat "to nearly half a million customers" — this is the source of the consultation's ~500,000-customer figure, *not* the renewables aggregate.
- **A manufacturing sector company.** A third, separately compromised target.

The technical vector in the renewables branch is the part of the incident most informative for UK designation policy. CERT Polska does not state how ownership of the 30 affected facilities was distributed (one portfolio operator, several, or many), and the report's reference to credential reuse "across multiple facilities" is offered as a plausible scaling hypothesis grounded in industry practice, not as a verified observation. What the report does confirm is a different and structurally more interesting common dependency: a small number of vendor product stacks ran across all 30 facilities, with vendor-shipped security defaults left in place.

The attacker exploited "Default" accounts on Hitachi RTU560 controllers, default SSH root on Mikronika RTUs, default FTP accounts on Hitachi Relion 650 protection relays (which vendor guidance had explicitly instructed operators to disable), default deployment passwords on Mikronika HMI Windows machines, and default login credentials on Moxa NPort serial servers — together with internet-exposed FortiGate VPN concentrators without multi-factor authentication, several with known historical RCE vulnerabilities unpatched (CERT.PL and Ministry of Digital Affairs, 2026, p. 7). No device was literally shared between operators; each facility ran its own equipment. What was common across the population was *vendor product monoculture combined with persistence of vendor-shipped defaults across independent deployments* — a dependency that exists regardless of how the 30 facilities' ownership is distributed, because every operator that procures the same vendor stack and leaves defaults in place inherits the same exposure. It is also a dependency that no individual operator can evidence or mitigate at sector level.

Two consequences for the UK regulatory primitive follow. First, none of the affected asset types individually approaches the existing NIS thresholds (≥ 2 GW cumulative generation; 250,000 final customers — Schedule 2, NIS Regulations 2018; consultation Table 1, p. 13); the threshold model treats each asset as an isolated unit and is, by construction, blind to the kind of correlated risk the Polish incident illustrates. Second, the term 'cumulative' in the threshold definition is underspecified: it is not stated whether generation capacity is cumulated within a single legal entity, a corporate group, or entities under common control. This creates a structural incentive for corporate fragmentation — an operator approaching the threshold can restructure into below-threshold entities without reducing aggregate attack surface. The aggregation-tier criterion proposed in section 3 addresses both defects: correlated risk does not dissolve at a corporate boundary, and the unit of analysis becomes the shared dependency rather than the legal entity. This is not an oversight in the 2018 design — it was a faithful reflection of a system in which a small number of large operators accounted for most generation and distribution — but it is a structural mismatch with the system the UK is now building.

The same observation applies to baseline coverage. Uniformly applying an IT-focused control set to over 1,400 licensed operators across the different licensed areas — each with radically different OT footprints — from a 50 MW community solar farm with cloud-managed telemetry, to a legacy interconnector with industrial control systems originally

commissioned in the 1990s — assumes both that the same minimum is meaningful for each and that it is achievable by each. Neither assumption holds at the level of detail that operational cyber resilience requires. The consultation itself acknowledges this for OT (p. 17) but frames the alternatives as case-by-case application of CE controls to OT, or — as the path it explicitly contemplates — a hybrid scheme with additional controls supplementing the five CE families (p. 17; Q10 asks whether consultees would develop a bespoke scheme on the same basis), rather than structural redesign of the regulatory primitive. Case-by-case adjudication is defensible for a small population of large NIS-designated operators; it does not scale to the growing population of smaller licensees the baseline regime is designed to cover.

3 COMPONENT A: AGGREGATION-TIER DESIGNATION

The proposed first component is aggregation-tier designation. The criterion for inclusion in NIS scope is the cumulative customer-impact or system-stability impact under a coordinated-compromise scenario across operators that share a critical dependency. 'Shared dependency' here is construed broadly: it covers literally shared instances (a common managed service provider, a common SCADA-as-a-service platform serving multiple operators) and structurally common but separately instantiated dependencies (the same vendor product deployed independently across operators; the same vendor-shipped default configuration left in place across operators; the same communications protocol whose vulnerabilities propagate across deployments). The Polish incident illustrates the second class. Designation under the aggregation-tier criterion applies irrespective of any individual operator's size.

Operationally this requires the joint Competent Authority (Ofgem and DESNZ) to maintain a register of shared critical dependencies. The register is populated from two sources: the OT context profile that each licensee maintains under Component B (described in section 4), which discloses major vendor and supplier dependencies; and the National Energy System Operator (NESO), whose statutory system-planning function under the Energy Act 2023 gives it visibility of technology concentrations across the operator population that no individual licensee or vendor possesses.

The Cyber Security and Resilience (Network and Information Systems) Bill, introduced to Parliament on 12 November 2025, provides the regulatory power to amend NIS applicability criteria (consultation p. 10). The aggregation-tier criterion is the substantive content that activates that power: a binding designation rule rather than a discretionary advisory.

Three design considerations follow from existing institutional architecture. First, NESO's role in the designation regime must be confined to technical input — supplier and dependency mapping, system-impact modelling, scenario analysis — without designation authority. NESO is, by statute, a system operator with operational dependencies on the same operator population whose designation it would otherwise be advising. Structural independence of designation advice is necessary to preserve the credibility of the regime, particularly in the event of a significant incident affecting a designated but under-regulated operator. Designation authority therefore remains with Ofgem, advised by NESO on technical questions and by an external panel — academic, retired sector engineers, NCSC representatives — on contested cases. The designation panel's proceedings — protocols and minutes — should be published as a matter of standard practice.

Second, the dependency-mapping exercise that populates the aggregation-tier register requires operators to disclose their SCADA platform choices, managed-service provider relationships, and shared telemetry infrastructure. If disclosure flows directly into a designation decision — such that reporting a shared critical dependency automatically triggers NIS scope — the rational operator response is to minimise or obscure disclosure, undermining the register's completeness. The architecture should therefore distinguish, as far as the underlying legal framework permits, the operational use of dependency disclosure (cluster detection, sector-wide vulnerability analysis, NESO system-impact modelling) from its evidential use in designation decisions and should be paired with proportionate confidentiality protections for commercially sensitive dependency data. The structural intuition is the learning-channel / enforcement-channel separation that operates in incident-reporting regimes, where conflating the two creates rational incentives for under-reporting (Shabad, 2026b). The precise mechanism — whether through statutory information-handling rules in the Cyber Security and Resilience Bill, internal Ofgem case-handling protocols, or a combination — is a question of UK administrative-law design that this paper does not attempt to resolve. What it establishes is that the disclosure incentive structure has to be solved before the dependency register can be populated honestly enough to be useful.

Third, the threshold should be unified across individual and aggregated operators — the same cumulative-impact metric applied whether the entity assessed is a single operator or a dependency cluster — and set explicitly as a function of Ofgem's supervisory capacity. This may at first reading appear circular: a threshold set by regulatory resource rather than by risk. The architecture deliberately separates the two questions and assigns them to different bodies. *Criticality* — what would cause material consequence to system stability or customer supply — is a technical question assessed by NESO, on the system-impact evidence its statutory planning function generates. *Designation* — which entities are brought into binding scope — is a regulatory question decided by Ofgem, constrained by the supervisory capacity Parliament funds. The two are connected but not collapsed: NESO's criticality ranking does not in itself impose obligations; Ofgem's designation does. This is the structural answer to the conflict-of-interest concern that a single body cannot both decide what is critical and decide how much critical infrastructure it can afford to supervise.

The honest framing is then that residual cyber risk in the sector grows or shrinks as a direct function of supervisory capacity at fixed criticality — and shrinks only if Parliament funds capacity to keep pace with the criticality NESO identifies. Expanding the scope of supervision at fixed resource produces compliance theatre, not resilience; the architecture refuses to disguise this trade-off.

The resource decision is not budgetary alone. DSIT documents that even a notional bottomless budget would not resolve the constraint, because the pool of qualified OT cyber security professionals is structurally insufficient: 'there are just not enough of us to go around, so even if we had all the money in the world, we couldn't recruit the people we needed' (DSIT, 2025, p. 27). Parliament's resource decision therefore encompasses workforce pipeline investment alongside supervisory funding.

The practical instrument is straightforward. Ofgem's annual report to Parliament should therefore include a supervisory capacity statement: current scope of effective supervision, the threshold implied by that capacity, and the residual risk carried by operators below the threshold. If Parliament judges the residual risk unacceptable, the remedy is additional supervisory resource; if Parliament prefers to reduce regulatory spending, the threshold rises and the residual risk is explicitly owned rather than silently accepted. This framing does not require the regulator to make the structurally awkward admission that supervisory ambition

exceeds capacity. It requires the risk–resource trade-off to be stated at the level — Parliament — where resource decisions are actually made.

4 COMPONENT B: OT SELF-TAILORING AS REGULATORY PRIMITIVE

The second component addresses what licensees are actually required to do.

The consultation proposes Cyber Essentials and CE+ as the starting reference for baseline cyber resilience across all Ofgem licensees, and supports the proposal with two pieces of evidence on the IT side: that certified organisations are 92 per cent less likely to make a cyber insurance claim, and that St James's Place observed an 80 per cent reduction in cyber security incidents after CE+ implementation (consultation p. 16). The 92 per cent insurance figure is plausibly informative about the broad opportunistic-threat tier, though it is downstream of insurer underwriting rules that themselves prefer certified estates and so cannot be read as a pure measure of resilience uplift. The St James's Place 80 per cent figure has no published verification trail in the IASME case study to which the consultation footnote points (IASME, 2024); 'cyber security incident' is not defined; and the count is necessarily subject to the same internal-judgement effects (which events are logged, escalated, and counted) that any single-firm self-reported reduction figure suffers from. The point is not that the consultation's evidence is wrong — it is that these are the IT-side success indicators of the IT-side instrument. None of them speaks to the OT exposures through which the Polish incident materialised, and on which the case for change rests. The consultation itself acknowledges the limit: "the Cyber Essentials scheme is primarily suitable for Information Technology (IT). Many operators in DGE rely on Operational Technology (OT) systems... It may be possible to apply Cyber Essentials controls to OT systems on a case-by-case basis, but their application can be challenging — and in certain circumstances unsuitable" (p. 17). Given that the harm pathway for distribution failures runs through OT — SCADA, programmable logic controllers, remote telemetry units, distributed sensor and actuator networks — and given that the December 2025 Polish incident materialised through precisely such OT exposures, an IT-primary baseline applied uniformly cannot be the operative regulatory primitive for the OT layer.

The consultation sets out two baseline paths: use the five Cyber Essentials control families as they are, or establish a hybrid scheme with additional controls tailored to Ofgem licensees (p. 17); Q10 asks whether consultees would go further and develop a bespoke scheme on the same basis. Supplementary principles the consultation lists for such a hybrid path could include IT/OT segregation, risk assessment, organisational policies and training, supply chain security, and response and recovery (p. 17). That hybrid path, however, runs into a problem deeper than heterogeneity: OT and IT operate under structurally inverted priority orderings. IT security prioritises confidentiality, then integrity, then availability. OT inverts this hierarchy — safety and continuous availability take precedence, and controls that are unremarkable in an IT context (forced reboots, aggressive patching cycles, endpoint security agents) 'may cause availability and timing disruptions' in OT that directly endanger physical processes and connected personnel (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023, section 2.4). Legacy OT systems compound this: many lack the computing resources to support encryption, error logging, or standard authentication mechanisms at all, irrespective of policy intent (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023, section 2.4). A hybrid scheme that presupposes control-logic compatibility across this inversion does not close the gap; it relocates it.

NIST SP 800-82r3 makes this explicit in its construction of the OT control overlay. Its Appendix F (OT Overlay against NIST SP 800-53 Rev 5) provides three impact-level baselines — Low, Moderate, and High — each comprising several dozen controls drawn from the NIST SP 800-53 Rev 5 control families and treats them not as mandatory floors but as starting points for tailoring. Section F.4 (Tailoring Considerations) makes compensating controls the rule rather than the exception:

Compensating controls in the OT environment may be required when the OT cannot support certain controls or control enhancements or when the organization determines that it is not advisable to implement controls or control enhancements due to potential adverse impacts to performance, safety, or reliability (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023, section F.4).

The consultation expressly invites evidence from stakeholders with operational OT experience as well as from academia and industry bodies (consultation pp. 6, 19). The

following observations are offered in that capacity. The author was previously responsible for OT cyber security capability at Eurasian Resources Group in Kazakhstan, a critical-infrastructure holding whose thermal generation assets supplied approximately 17 per cent of national electricity and whose OT estates also spanned mining and primary processing — a portfolio whose technological heterogeneity (multi-generation SCADA, mixed criticality, mixed maintenance cadence) is structurally analogous to the post-2030 GB DGE estate the consultation describes, even though the regulatory and ownership context is different. The intent is not to transplant a non-UK regime, but to surface the constraints that this paper's architectural recommendations are designed to accommodate and that uniform-control regimes systematically do not. That holding's SCADA estate spanned approximately four generations of vendor systems, ranging from current platforms to systems commissioned in the 1990s. For systems in the oldest generation, vendor support had long expired: no patches were available regardless of maintenance window, and updating SCADA software was inseparable from updating the physical equipment it controls — making refresh cycles a capital investment decision rather than a cyber policy one. For current-generation systems, patching was bounded by scheduled maintenance windows recurring on quarterly cycles at best. Cyber human resource was structurally scarce throughout.

These constraints are not specific to one holding. NIST SP 800-82r3 identifies patch unavailability as a structural feature of the OT sector: 'many OT utilize older versions of OSs that are no longer supported by the vendor through patches' (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023, section 2.4). The human resource constraint is confirmed as universal across CNI sectors regardless of budget by (DSIT, 2025). Under these conditions, a uniform mandatory control list does not produce uniform defence. It produces a forced misallocation of scarce expertise: cyber resource is rationally directed at documenting nominal control achievement for external assurance rather than at retiring the security debt that drives actual operational risk. The compliance certificate becomes a positional artefact whose informational content about defensive capability is low.

The proposed second component reverses the regulatory design. The regulator does not prescribe a uniform control list. The regulator prescribes an entry artefact and a tailoring discipline. Each licensee with an OT footprint maintains, on a defined renewal cycle:

1. **A consequence/criticality analysis**, anchored to the Consequence-driven Cyber-informed Engineering methodology (NIST SP 800-82r3 Appendix D.2.7) —

identifying which operational consequences would result from compromise of which assets, and what can be engineered out (decoupled, isolated, manually-failoverable) versus what must be defended.

2. **An asset inventory mapped to Purdue Reference Model levels**, with explicit data flows between levels and documented segregation boundaries.
3. **A tailored control selection from a recognised reference** — NCSC Cyber Assessment Framework (CAF) v4.0, NIST SP 800-82r3 Appendix F, or IEC 62443-2-1 and 62443-3-3 — with documented rationale for each compensating-control deviation from the reference baseline.
4. **A Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) for all newly procured OT components**, maintained as a cryptographically signed, machine-readable artefact and paired with automated CVE-matching tooling. SBOM does not resolve the legacy patch-unavailability problem documented above, but it creates the visibility layer that makes automated vulnerability analysis tractable: newly disclosed CVEs can be systematically matched against declared component inventories without manual triage. The NCSC notes that unsigned SBOMs offer no verifiable trust and that the instrument's value depends on accuracy and pairing with vulnerability scanning (NCSC, 2024); the procurement condition should therefore specify both signing and tooling as requirements, not the artefact alone. This directly operationalises the vulnerability closure rate metric in Component C. Where a shared SBOM component is identified across multiple licensees, it also populates the shared-dependency register that underpins aggregation-tier designation in Component A — connecting Component B's asset-level disclosure function to Component A's cluster-detection function.

The implementation cost at small-licensee scale is non-trivial and is structurally the same trade-off as the supervisory-capacity question in section 3: dependency visibility into shared OT components is the principal instrument by which systemic correlated risk becomes detectable; lower procurement burden on small operators reduces visibility into precisely the part of the estate the consultation is most concerned to bring into scope. The honest treatment is to declare the trade-off — visibility vs cost at small-licensee scale, phasing of the procurement condition, threshold above which signing-and-tooling is required — to Parliament alongside the supervisory-capacity statement, rather than resolving it silently in implementation guidance.

What the regulator assures is the defensibility of the tailoring: is the consequence analysis serious, is the control selection coherent with it, are the compensating controls justified, are deviations from the reference baseline traceable? The regulator does not measure achievement against a uniform list — because in real heterogeneous OT estates that achievement, against a uniform list, is a fiction.

This is an outcome-based assessment requiring informed regulatory judgement rather than checklist verification — the methodology the NCSC already applies in CAF assessments and that the PRA applies in outcomes-based financial supervision. The operative standard is not 'did the licensee implement control X?' but 'would a competent, independent OT security professional find this tailoring rationale substantive and this compensating-control justification adequate given the documented operational constraints?' The audit object is the tailoring package — consequence analysis, asset inventory, control rationale, SBOM — not a certificate of control achievement. This shifts the regulatory burden from proving a universal minimum to demonstrating a defensible, evidence-grounded position: a standard that heterogeneous OT estates can actually meet, and that regulators can meaningfully evaluate without needing to prescribe the content of every control.

5 COMPONENT C: VELOCITY-BASED ASSURANCE WITH SECTORAL THREAT- INTELLIGENCE ANCHOR

The third component addresses what gets reported, audited, and used to migrate operators between regulatory tiers.

The consultation proposes static positional assurance: Cyber Essentials certification at a fixed reporting date for the baseline; full CAF audit for NIS scope; and a deferred "intermediate" tier left for a future workstream. This is positional attainment in the standard regulatory sense — the controls are in place at the reporting date, or they are not. Static positional assurance applied to a non-static threat environment has a documented failure mode: well-resourced operators do not systematically outperform smaller ones on static measures, because the complexity of securing a digital estate grows non-linearly with estate size and absorbs additional resource (Shabad, 2026a). This dynamic is structurally present in DGE under

Clean Power 2030, with the added complication that the digital estate is growing in operator number as well as in per-operator complexity.

The proposed third component replaces static positional reporting with velocity reporting against the tailored profile (Component B). Three measured dimensions:

- **Vulnerability closure rate**, weighted by OT asset criticality from the Component B consequence analysis (rather than weighted by CVSS score, which does not reflect operational consequence).
- **Security debt retirement**, measured against the documented compensating-control register from the Component B tailoring rationale.
- **Adaptive response capacity**, demonstrated through participation in sectoral exercises calibrated to current threats rather than through self-assessment.

These three dimensions instantiate the Cyber Progress Measure framework (Shabad, 2026a) in the DGE sector context. The justification for measuring velocity rather than position rests on the ecological-rationality argument that in dynamic environments, simple directional heuristics outperform complex state-based rules (Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier, 2011); and on the Red Queen dynamic (Van Valen, 1973), in which a static defensive posture in a continuously-evolving adversarial environment constitutes regression, not stasis.

Velocity without a directional signal is undirected motion. The proposed third component is therefore conditioned on a sectoral threat-intelligence function: a joint NCSC–NESO Energy Threat Operations capability, structurally analogous to the NHS Cyber Security Operations Centre, scoped to DGE. NCSC has the cyber-threat expertise and operates the CAF v4.0 framework already referenced in the consultation (footnote 9); NESO has the system-impact visibility (consultation footnote 21). The combined function produces a prioritised indicator-of-compromise feed and tactical and strategic assessments specific to threats actually targeting UK energy infrastructure — telling operators not merely that they must improve, but where this quarter's improvement effort should be concentrated. Each operator retains responsibility for closing vulnerabilities and retiring security debt against its tailored profile; the sectoral feed ensures that local effort is focused on attack vectors currently materialising, not on last year's compliance checklist.

Migration between regulatory tiers is then triggered by combined criteria: aggregation-tier impact (Component A) and velocity falling below the sectoral median against the threat-anchored profile, sustained over a defined assessment window. The Cyber Security and Resilience Bill amendment powers become an adaptive instrument rather than a political one.

6 THE INTEGRATION THESIS

The three components are not separable. Each pairwise omission produces a specific, predictable failure.

- **A without B (designation expanded, controls unchanged).** Aggregation-tier designation captures clusters of small distributed renewable operators whose OT footprints are precisely the population for which IT-style baselines and uniform mandatory lists are least applicable. Newly-designated operators are pushed into certification regimes whose controls are misaligned with their OT estate; scarce cyber resource is redirected from retiring genuine security debt to producing certification evidence. The regime extends its perimeter, the audited operator count rises, and the actual defensive posture against the next coordinated-compromise attempt does not improve. This is the standard regulatory-extension-without-control-redesign failure mode.
- **A without C (designation expanded, assurance static).** Once newly-captured clusters complete first-cycle certification, there is no instrument that distinguishes a cluster that is closing vulnerabilities ahead of the threat curve from a cluster that achieved compliance at the reporting date and stopped. Migration logic between tiers collapses to renewal of position rather than measurement of trajectory; the regime cannot tell, at the moment a coordinated attack arrives, whether the cluster's defensive state is the certified state or an unmaintained drift from it.
- **B without A (controls redesigned, designation unchanged).** OT self-tailoring applied only to operators above existing NIS thresholds leaves the correlated-risk mechanism — the principal vulnerability that the Polish incident illustrates — entirely outside the controls layer. The licensees with the strongest tailoring discipline are the ones least likely to be the entry vector for a distributed-asset coordinated compromise.
- **B without C (controls tailored, assurance static).** Tailoring is by construction operator-specific; without an assurance instrument that measures movement against

the tailored profile, the regulator has no means to distinguish defensible tailoring from self-justifying minima. Static positional assessment of tailored profiles becomes "did the operator do what the operator's own document said it would do", which is a tautology, not assurance.

- **C without A (velocity measured on the wrong population).** Velocity reporting against the tailored profile, applied only to operators above the existing thresholds, optimises adaptation rate among the large concentrated operators and ignores it among the distributed clusters that are the documented attack target.
- **C without B (velocity measured against an unfit baseline).** Velocity against a uniform IT-style control list produces high-velocity compliance theatre — fast closure of CVSS-prioritised vulnerabilities that are not the OT-criticality-weighted vulnerabilities actually material to the operator's safety case.

Each component is therefore the corrective to a specific failure mode of the others. Adopting any one or two of the three produces a regime that is internally consistent at its perimeter but predictably brittle along the dimension the omitted component would have addressed.

The architecture is also more deferential to the existing institutional ecosystem than first appears. NCSC retains the technical framework function. NESO retains the system-planning function. Ofgem retains designation authority. The Cyber Security and Resilience Bill provides the regulatory power. What changes is the substantive content of designation, the regulatory primitive at the control layer, and the assurance instrument — not the institutional distribution of authority. The reform is definitional, not constitutional. It uses existing institutions in their existing competencies; it changes what those institutions are asked to produce.

7 PORTABILITY BEYOND DGE

The architecture is portable. The same three components — correlation-aware designation, self-tailoring against a recognised reference, velocity-based assurance with a sectoral intelligence anchor — apply structurally to any regulated critical-infrastructure sector with heterogeneous OT estates, distributed operator populations, and active threat development: water and wastewater, downstream oil and gas, transport (rail, ports, aviation), and digital

infrastructure. The argument here is anchored on DGE because the present consultation makes DGE its object; the mechanism is general.

Two elements do not transfer cleanly. First, the specific reference set named in Component B (CAF, 800-82r3, 62443) is not jurisdiction-neutral: the CAF is a UK reference, 800-82r3 is a US federal reference, and 62443 is international. Sectors regulated under other jurisdictions would substitute equivalents. Second, the joint authority structure (Ofgem + DESNZ + NCSC + NESO) is a UK-specific quartet whose distribution of statutory competencies does not exist in other jurisdictions in the same combination. The architectural principle — separate designation, tailoring, and assurance authorities with structurally independent advisory roles — transfers; the specific institutional allocation does not.

8 CALIBRATION QUESTIONS LEFT OPEN

The architectural argument set out here is deliberately framed at the level of regulatory primitives. It does not close the operational calibration questions that necessarily follow. Those questions are properly the subject of sector-specific work, and the four institutional participants typically named — the joint Competent Authority, NESO, the licensee population, and OT vendors — hold most of the expertise required. Each, however, occupies a partial vantage point: the Authority is staffed for regulatory design and supervisory practice; NESO for system planning; vendors for product engineering; licensees for their own estates. Calibration of the three load-bearing parameters below benefits from cross-cutting input drawn from outside that quartet — cross-operator OT security operations experience at CNI scale, combined with enterprise-architecture practice in regulated environments and direct familiarity with the OT reference frameworks named in Component B (CAF, NIST SP 800-82r3, IEC 62443). The UK already has an established mechanism for channelling that kind of contribution: the NCSC Industry 100 (i100) scheme, under which industry secondees work part-time alongside NCSC while remaining employed and paid by their home organisations to preserve independence. The scheme has grown to roughly 160 secondees, with the energy sector now its most heavily represented constituency and is rated 'valuable' to 'indispensable' by over 80 per cent of NCSC hosts (NCSC, 2025). The three calibration questions:

1. **Aggregation-tier triggering criteria (Component A).** At what number of operators sharing a critical dependency, and under what assumed coordinated-compromise success rate, does a dependency cluster cross into NIS scope? What methodology — scenario library, attack-graph modelling, NESO system-impact simulation, or a combination — should generate the cumulative-impact figure against the unified threshold? How should the threshold be re-tested as the dependency graph evolves with the energy transition?
2. **Velocity-metric specification (Component C).** What units, reporting cadence, and assessment window apply to vulnerability closure rate weighted by OT-asset criticality, and to security-debt retirement? How is the 'sectoral median' against which migration is judged constructed so that it does not mechanically punish low-velocity peer cohorts of operators with adequate absolute velocity against the threat-intelligence-anchored profile? What treatment of pre-window surge behaviour preserves the assurance value of the velocity instrument?
3. **SBOM procurement condition at small-licensee scale (Component B).** At what licensee scale and what OT component class does the signing-and-tooling requirement attach? What phasing applies to retrofit versus new procurement? How is the trade-off between dependency visibility and implementation burden at sub-NIS operator scale resolved — and made transparent to Parliament alongside the supervisory-capacity statement?

These are operational questions, not architectural ones. They are answerable through targeted analytical work calibrated to the GB DGE estate's actual dependency structure, vendor concentration, and licensee population, informed by practitioner input of the cross-cutting profile described above. The author is one such practitioner (see 'About the Author') and would welcome contributing to that work through i100 or an equivalent route, alongside the wider community of OT security practitioners the scheme already convenes. Leaving the questions open in this paper is a deliberate choice: closing them prematurely, on the limited dependency data publicly available and without the cross-operator analytical work this calibration requires, would substitute the appearance of operational specificity for the analysis the question actually requires.

9 CONCLUSION

The DESNZ/Ofgem proposals to expand NIS coverage and to introduce a baseline for all Ofgem licensees address the right structural problem. The construction, however, retains the regulatory primitives calibrated for a concentrated energy system that no longer exists. The three-component architecture set out here — aggregation-tier designation, OT self-tailoring, velocity-based assurance — replaces the primitives without replacing the institutions. It uses existing UK cyber-regulatory powers (the Cyber Security and Resilience Bill, the CAF framework, NESO's system-planning mandate, Ofgem's designation authority) in their existing form, while changing the substantive content of what is designated, what is required, and what is measured, without redrawing the institutional map. The cost of not making it is the uniform extension, across a much larger and more distributed operator population, of a regulatory model whose limitations the consultation itself identifies.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

The author is an independent researcher at the University of Liverpool (CISSP, CCSP, FBSC) writing in a personal capacity. He was previously responsible for operational-technology cyber security capability at Eurasian Resources Group, a critical-infrastructure operator in Kazakhstan generating approximately 17 per cent of national electricity supply through a heterogeneous holding portfolio of thermal generation, mining, and primary processing assets. He currently works as a Principal Enterprise Architect at a FTSE 100 company. This working paper is published as a companion to a response submitted to the DESNZ/Ofgem consultation *Reshaping Cyber Regulation in Downstream Gas and Electricity* on 22 May 2026.

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PERSONAL CAPACITY

The views expressed are those of the author in a personal capacity and do not represent the positions of any organisations the author is or has been associated with.